

THE STANDARD EUROPEAN VECTOR ARCHITECTURE (SEVA) PLASMID

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Abstract. *The Standard European Vector Architecture (SEVA) plasmid has emerged as a foundational resource in the field of synthetic biology and genetic engineering. With its standardized design principles and versatile functionalities, SEVA plasmids have facilitated the construction of genetic circuits, the development of biotechnological applications, and the advancement of scientific research. In this article, we delve into the SEVA plasmid system, exploring its history, design, key features, and diverse applications. We also discuss the future prospects and potential impact of SEVA plasmids in shaping the future of genetic engineering.*

Key words: *Plasmid design, SEVA cargo, origin of replication*

Аннотация. *Плазмида стандартной европейской векторной архитектуры (SEVA) стала основополагающим ресурсом в области синтетической биологии и генной инженерии. Благодаря стандартизированным принципам проектирования и универсальным функциональным возможностям плазмиды SEVA облегчили создание генетических цепей, разработку биотехнологических приложений и развитие научных исследований. В этой статье мы углубимся в плазмидную систему SEVA, изучая ее историю, конструкцию, ключевые особенности и разнообразные применения. Мы также обсуждаем будущие перспективы и потенциальное влияние плазмид SEVA на формирование будущего генной инженерии.*

Ключевые слова: *Плазмидный дизайн, карго SEVA, начало репликации*

Annotatsiya. *Standart Yevropa vektor arxitekturasi (SEVA) plazmidi sintetik biologiya va genetik muhandislik sohasida asosiy hisoblanadi. Standartlashtirilgan dizayn tamoyillari va bir qancha funksiyalari bilan SEVA plazmidlari genetik tuzilmalarni qurish, biotexnologik ilovalarni ishlab chiqish va ilmiy tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirishga yordam berdi. Ushbu maqolada biz SEVA plazmid tizimini o'rganamiz, uning tarixi, dizayni, asosiy xususiyatlari va turli xil ilovalarini o'rganamiz. Shuningdek, biz genetik muhandislik kelajagini shakllantirishda SEVA plazmidlarining kelajak istiqbollari va potentsial ta'sirini muhokama qilamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Plazmida dizayn, SEVA cargo, replikatsiya kelib chiqishi*

Introduction. The field of synthetic biology has witnessed remarkable advancements in recent years, driven by the development of standardized tools and resources that enable the efficient manipulation of genetic information. Among these tools, the Standard European Vector Architecture (SEVA) plasmid system has garnered significant attention for its role in simplifying genetic engineering processes and promoting reproducibility in research. Most of the scientific work in the field of genetic engineering is carried out in *Escherichia coli*. In recent decades [1-3], many attempts have been made to expand the vector toolkit beyond enteric bacteria to include a wide range of plasmids [4], transposons, and transposon-vectors [5-7] takes.

SEVA Plasmid Design.

The SEVA plasmid design is characterized by its modularity and compatibility, allowing researchers to assemble genetic constructs with ease. Key features of SEVA plasmids include:

Standardized Parts: SEVA plasmids consist of standardized genetic components, such as promoters, ribosome binding sites, and terminators. These elements adhere to specific rules and nomenclature, simplifying their use in genetic circuit design.

Broad Compatibility: SEVA plasmids are compatible with a wide range of organisms, making them versatile tools for diverse applications, including prokaryotes and eukaryotes.

Expression Control: Researchers can fine-tune gene expression levels using a variety of SEVA-compatible promoters and inducible systems, allowing for precise control over genetic circuits.

At the heart of the SEVA plasmid system is its modular design, which encompasses the following key components: (Figure 1.) [8]

Standardized Genetic Parts: SEVA plasmids incorporate a library of standardized genetic elements, including promoters, ribosome binding sites (RBS), and terminators. These elements adhere to specific naming conventions and design principles, ensuring compatibility and ease of use.

Origin of Replication (ori): SEVA plasmids employ various origins of replication, allowing them to replicate in a wide range of bacterial hosts. This versatility is a hallmark of SEVA's design.

Selection Markers: SEVA plasmids feature a selection marker, often an antibiotic resistance gene, which aids in the maintenance and selection of plasmids in host organisms.

Modular Assembly: SEVA plasmids can be readily assembled using a standardized approach, enabling researchers to mix and match genetic components to create custom genetic circuits.

Figure 1.

General organization of the structure of SEVA plasmids. SEVA vectors are formed by three variable modules: cargo (blue), origin of replication (green) and antibiotic marker (purple). The enzymes used to modify the functional DNA segments are shown in the same color code, and the modules are separated by three constant regions shared by all vectors, the T0 and T1

transcription terminators and the oriT conjugation origin. All universal primers (PS1–PS6) are placed on the invariant backbone and used to sequence/verify the variable modules.

Applications of SEVA Plasmids.

SEVA plasmids have found applications in various domains:

Biotechnology: SEVA plasmids have been instrumental in the development of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) for bioproduction, enabling the synthesis of valuable compounds such as biofuels, pharmaceuticals, and enzymes.

Environmental Remediation: SEVA plasmids are employed in the design of microbial systems for environmental cleanup, including bioremediation of pollutants and heavy metals.

Basic Research: SEVA plasmids have advanced our understanding of fundamental biological processes by allowing researchers to construct and manipulate genetic circuits with precision.

Nomenclature of the pSEVA plasmids

All vectors are called pSEVA by polynomial notation,

The first column of the code reflects the resistance to antibiotics. (Figure 2)

Figure 2.

The codes contained in SEVA plasmids consist of three sequences: the first is the antibiotic marker, the second is the origin of replication, and the third is the cargo [9]. Each plasmid contains a corresponding list of codes, in addition, additional numbers and letters are used to designate different modifications of the cargo.

Types of origins of replication.

There are lots of origins of replication out there so, for simplicity's sake, we've ignored those used in eukaryotic cells and viruses and focused only on those found in bacteria. Generally, control of replication is referred to as "relaxed" or "[stringent](#)" depending on whether the *ori* is positively regulated by RNA or proteins, respectively [10]. A plasmid's copy number has to do with the balance between positive and negative regulation and can be manipulated with mutations in the replicon. For example, the pMB1 *ori* maintains about 20 copies per cell, while pUC – which differs by only two mutations – will produce as many as 700 copies per cell. (Figure 3). As a rule, plasmids from the same group should not be co-transformed, so if you need two plasmids for an experiment, make sure they have "compatible" *ori*'s. See the table below for more details.

Figure 3.

Common Vectors	Copy Number ⁺	<i>ori</i>	Incompatibility Group	Control
pUC	~500-700	pMB1 (derivative)	A	Relaxed
pBR322	~15-20	pMB1	A	Relaxed
pET	~15-20	pBR322	A	Relaxed
pGEX	~15-20	pBR322	A	Relaxed
pColE1	~15-20	ColE1	A	Relaxed
pR6K	~15-20	R6K*	C	Stringent
pACYC	~10	p15A	B	Relaxed
pSC101	~5	pSC101	C	Stringent
pBluescript	~300-500	ColE1 (derivative) and F1**	A	Relaxed
pGEM	~300-500	pUC and F1**	A	Relaxed

Future Prospects

The SEVA plasmid system is poised for continued growth and impact in the field of synthetic biology. Some key future prospects include:

Standardization Efforts: Ongoing efforts to expand and refine the SEVA plasmid system, incorporating new genetic elements and enhancing compatibility with additional organisms.

Biosecurity and Ethics: The widespread use of SEVA plasmids also raises questions about biosecurity and ethical considerations, prompting discussions on responsible genetic engineering practices.

Education and Outreach: SEVA plasmids offer a valuable platform for education and outreach in synthetic biology, helping train the next generation of scientists and engineers.

Conclusion

The Standard European Vector Architecture (SEVA) plasmid system has revolutionized genetic engineering by providing a standardized, modular, and versatile platform for the construction of genetic circuits and the development of biotechnological applications. As SEVA plasmids continue to evolve and find new applications, they hold great promise in shaping the future of synthetic biology and genetic engineering, enabling innovative solutions to global challenges and fostering responsible research practices.

The SEVA format kit, for example, allows the propagation of gram-positive organisms by including fragments. Nowadays, cargo genetic mobile elements, new expression devices,

monitoring and detection systems of protein-protein interaction and other processes are being expanded in laboratories [11, 12, 13]. By adopting the SEVA format, a large number of bacteria other than *E. coli* could be programmed, and it facilitated the transition to synthetic biology based on genetic engineering. In addition, the SEVA vector construction has the ability to change some parts, unlike other simple vector constructions.

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